

FARMER'S PERCEPTION ABOUT LINK MARKETING OF AGROCHEMICALS IN CHANDRAPUR DISTRICT

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Abstract

India's agricultural sector plays a critical role in sustaining over half of the country's population, with agrochemicals being essential tools for protecting crops from pests and improving yield. The Chandrapur district, a significant agricultural region in Maharashtra, relies heavily on these chemicals, particularly for cotton production. However, link marketing-where agrochemicals are bundled with supplementary products-poses challenges for farmers. While the agrochemical market is growing rapidly, farmers often face issues such as high costs, limited access, and lack of knowledge about the effective use of these products, leading to potential health risks and environmental damage. This study explores farmers' perceptions of the link marketing of agrochemicals in Chandrapur district, focusing on the socio-economic factors that influence their decisions and the difficulties they face in using these chemicals effectively.

The study, conducted in six villages, involved a survey of 60 farmers, supplemented by focus group discussions to gain deeper insights. The findings reveal that most farmers are aware of the benefits of agrochemicals but are concerned about the extra costs and forced purchases of linked products. Their limited access to quality agrochemicals and credit, coupled with the pressure to buy additional products, often leads to financial strain. The study underscores the need for more transparent and sustainable marketing practices that support farmers' livelihoods and promote environmental health in the region.

Keywords: Link products, Agrochemicals, Farmers, Perception, Agriculture, Cropping pattern, etc.

Introduction and Objectives

India, being an agrarian economy, has over 50% of its population reliant on agriculture for livelihood. The country is a global leader in the production of several agricultural commodities, including spices, pulses, and tea, while also ranking second in the production of wheat, rice, and vegetables. A key component of modern agriculture in India is the use of agrochemicals (crop protection products), which are essential for safeguarding crops from pests, diseases, and weeds. These chemicals play a significant role in maintaining food production levels and improving crop yields. Without agrochemicals, crop losses could significantly increase.

India is currently the fourth-largest producer of agrochemicals worldwide, with a growing domestic and export market. The agrochemical market in India reached USD 6.51 billion in 2023 and is expected to grow at a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 8.5% from 2024 to 2032. In regions like Chandrapur district, Maharashtra, which has a strong agricultural heritage, agrochemicals are crucial for sustaining crop production. However, challenges related to the availability, affordability, and safe usage of these chemicals persist, alongside concerns about environmental and health impacts. The study seeks to explore these issues, focusing on farmers' perceptions and the marketing of agrochemicals in the region.

The specific objectives of the study are:

1. To study Socio-economic characteristics of selected farmers.
2. To evaluate the requirement of agro-chemical product and received excess linked products.
3. To assess farmers perception about linked products.

Materials and Methods

The methodology of this research focuses on selecting six villages from two talukas in Chandrapur district, where data was collected during the financial year 2023-24. A total of 60 farmers participated in the study, with 10 farmers chosen from each village. The primary data collection process involved direct interactions with the farmers to capture their socio-economic and agricultural practices. Various statistical tools, such as descriptive statistics and regression analysis, were employed to analyze the data and extract meaningful insights related to the research objectives. This systematic approach ensures the

Table 1: Distribution of Family Size of Selected Farmers

Sr. No.	Category	No. of farmers	Percent Share
1	Small (Up to 3)	21	35.00
2	Medium (4-6)	38	63.33
3	Large (above 6)	1	1.67

reliability and accuracy of the findings, making the study robust and comprehensive in addressing the research problem.

Analytical tools**Variables to study socio-economic status of farmers**

1. Family size
2. Family income
3. Education
4. Age
5. Land holding
6. Category
7. Social media access
8. Availability of resources
9. Knowledge on mitigation and adaption practices in agriculture
10. Farming experience

Evaluation of required agro-chemical products and received excess linked products.

The evaluation of requiring agro-chemicals and receiving excess linked products will be on the basis of the data that will be collected from farmers of the Chandrapur district.

Evaluation of farmers perception about link products.

The farmers perception will be analyzed by means of tabular analysis of collected data on the basis of following variables:

1. Extra cost
2. Awareness
3. Credit period
4. Useful
5. Result
6. Source of purchase
7. Forcefully purchase

Results and Discussion

The present study has been undertaken with the view to know the "Farmer's perception about link marketing of agrochemicals in Chandrapur district." The data related to the farmers was collected, organized, and analysed to meet the study's objectives. The results obtained are presented and discussed in a logical sequence as follows.

The Socio-economic characteristics of selected farmers.

Family size also plays a critical role in understanding the social dynamics of this group. The table(1) indicates that most farmers come from medium-sized families, with 63.33% (38 farmers) belonging to households with 4-6 members. Small families, comprising up to 3 members, account for 35% (21 farmers), while only 1.67% (1 farmer)

has a large family with more than six members. The predominance of medium-sized families might reflect an alignment between agricultural labor requirements and family structure, with these families having the necessary support for farm work without being overly burdened by high dependency ratios.

Table 2: Distribution of Selected Farmers on the Basis of Annual Income

Sr. No.	Category (in lakhs)	No. of farmers	Percentage share	Average income per farmer (in lakhs)
1	Up to 5	21	35.00	2.5
2	5-10	29	48.33	7.5
3	10-15	4	6.67	12
4	15 and above	6	10.00	17

The table (2) categorizes farmers based on their annual income, showing that 35% (21 farmers) earn up to INR 5 lakhs, with an average income of INR 250,000, representing lower-income farmers who may struggle with profitability. The largest group, comprising 48.33% (29 farmers), earns between INR 5 to 10 lakhs, with an average income of

INR 750,000, indicating moderate financial stability. A smaller 6.67% (4 farmers) earns INR 10 to 15 lakhs, averaging INR 1,200,000, likely reflecting optimized farming practices. Lastly, 10% (6 farmers) earn over INR 15 lakhs, with an average income of INR 1,700,000, likely representing large-scale or diversified farmers.

Table 3: Distribution of Selected Farmers on the Basis of Education

Sr. No.	Category	No. of farmers	Percent share
1	Illiterate	Nil	Nil
2	1-7 Standards	3	5.00
3	8-12 Standards	44	73.33
4	Graduate Level	13	21.66

The table(3) indicates the education levels among the farmers reveal a promising trend towards literacy and basic schooling. While there are no illiterate farmers, the majority (73.33%, or 44 farmers) have completed education between 8th and 12th standards, which indicates a reasonable level of schooling. Graduate- level education is observed

in 21.66% (13 farmers), while 5% (3 farmers) have schooling up to 1-7 standards. The educational profile suggests that these farmers possess the necessary literacy and numeracy skills to engage with modern farming techniques and market information, contributing to better farm management and decision-making.

Table 4: Distribution of Selected Farmers on the Basis of Age

Sr. No.	Category	No. of farmers	Percent share
1	Adult (26-44 age)	15	25.00
2	Middle aged (45-59 age)	35	58.34
3	Old aged (60 & above)	10	16.66

The table(4) reveals that a majority of the farmers belong to the middle-aged category, with 58.34% (35 farmers), while 25% (15 farmers) are young, and 16.66% (10 farmers) are classified as old. This data suggests that the farming community is primarily driven by individuals

in their most productive years, indicating the role of middle-aged farmers in sustaining agricultural activities. The relatively low percentage of old-aged farmers hints at possible generational shifts or labor- intensive challenges faced by older individuals in farming.

Table 5: Distribution of Selected Farmers on the Basis of Land Holding

Sr. No.	Category	No. of farmers	Percent Share	Average (Acre)
1	Marginal (Up to 2.5 Acre)	0	0	9.38
2	Small (2.5 to 5 Acre)	10	16.66	
3	Medium (5 to 10 Acre)	37	61.67	
4	Large (10 and above)	13	21.67	

The table(5) categorizes farmers based on landholding size, showing no marginal farmers (0%) with holdings of up to 2.5 acres, even though the average land size is 9.38 acres. Small farmers, with 2.5 to 5 acres, make up 16.66% of the group (10 farmers), reflecting a minority operating smaller plots. The majority, 61.67% (37 farmers), have

medium-sized farms between 5 and 10 acres, highlighting the centrality of medium landholdings in this group. Large farmers, with over 10 acres, represent 21.67% (13 farmers), suggesting a skew toward medium and large landholdings in this population.

Table 6: Distribution if Selected Farmers on the Basis of Category

Sr. No	Category	No. of farmers	Percent share
1	OBC	45	75.00
2	SC/ST	15	25.00

In table (6) in terms of caste composition, a significant proportion of the farmers, 75% (45 farmers), belong to the Other Backward Classes (OBC), while 25% (15 farmers) come from Scheduled Castes (SC) or

Scheduled Tribes (ST). This data highlights the representation of marginalized communities within the farming sector and potentially suggests a focus on inclusive policies that support these groups.

Table 7: Distribution of Selected Farmers on the Basis of Social Media Access and Knowledge on New Agricultural Technology and Availability of Resources

Sr. No.	Particulars	No. of farmers	Percent share
1	Social Media access	44	73.34
2	Awareness of new technology	59	98.34
3	Availability of resources	38	63.33

The data from table (7) reveals that 73.34% of farmers (44 out of 60) have access to social media, indicating a rising trend in using digital platforms for sharing agricultural information and market updates, which enhances communication within the farming community. Furthermore, an impressive 98.34% (59 farmers) are aware of new agricultural technologies, showcasing the effectiveness of various information channels such as extension services and Farmer Producer

Organizations (FPOs) in promoting modern farming techniques. However, only 63.33% (38 farmers) report access to essential agricultural resources like inputs and tools, highlighting a gap between awareness and resource availability that may hinder the practical application of these technological advancements due to financial, logistical, or infrastructural challenges.

Table 8: Distribution of Selected Farmers on the Basis of Farming Experience

Sr. No.	Farming experience (in yrs.)	No of farmers	Percent share
1	0-10	18	30.00
2	11-20	20	33.34
3	21-30	12	20.00
4	31-40	8	13.33
5	41 & above	2	3.34

The data reveals the distribution of farming experience among farmers, showing that 30% (18 farmers) have 0-10 years of experience, highlighting a significant number of new entrants in agriculture. The largest group, at 33.34% (20 farmers), falls within the 11-20 year bracket, indicating a solid base of moderately experienced farmers. Additionally, 20% (12 farmers) have 21-30 years of experience,

representing a cohort with substantial agricultural knowledge. A smaller segment, 13.33% (8 farmers), has 31-40 years of experience, while only 3.34% (2 farmers) have been farming for over 41 years. This distribution underscores a concentration of farmers with less than 30 years of experience.

Table 9: Identification of Cropping Pattern of Selected Farmers

Sr. No.	Crops sown	Average (acre/farmer)	Percentage share
Kharif Crops			
1	Cotton (Irrigated)	4.78	16.70
2	Cotton (non-irrigated)	4.74	13.60
3	Soybean (Irrigated)	2.61	11.70
4	Soybean (non-irrigated)	3.10	5.32
5	Paddy (Irrigated)	2.60	8.36
6	Paddy (non-irrigated)	1.75	0.37

Sr. No.	Crops sown	Average (acre/farmer)	Percentage share
Rabi Crops			
1	Chickpea	4.79	30.15
2	Wheat	2.07	11.93
3	Others	1.00	0.17

The overview of crop cultivation in Chandrapur district during the Kharif and Rabi seasons reveals significant trends in agricultural practices. In the Kharif season, irrigated cotton stands out as the leading crop, with farmers dedicating an average of 4.78 acres, representing 16.70% of the total crop share, closely followed by non-irrigated cotton at 4.74 acres (13.60%). Soybean also features prominently, particularly in irrigated conditions, while paddy is cultivated on smaller plots, highlighting water availability as a crucial

factor in crop selection. Transitioning to the Rabi season, chickpea emerges as the dominant crop, with farmers allocating 4.79 acres per farmer, accounting for 30.15% of the total share. Wheat follows as the second-most cultivated Rabi crop, indicating the district's reliance on cotton and chickpea, and underscoring the influence of irrigation on agricultural choices.

The requirement of agro-chemical product and received excess linked products.

Table 10: Fertilizers utilization of selected farmers

Sr. No.	Fertilizer	Utilization (In Kg.)	Per acre utilization (In Kg.)	Percentage share
1	DAP (50 Kg/Bag)	31525	81.77	24.96
2	SSP	32150	112.60	25.45

	(50 Kg/Bag)			
3	UREA (45 Kg/Bag)	28372.5	99.37	22.46
4	10-26-26 (50 Kg/Bag)	19350	67.77	15.32
	20-20-0-13 (50 Kg/Bag)	12125	42.47	9.60
	18-18-10 (50 Kg/Bag)	1050	3.68	0.83
5	MOP (50 Kg/Bag)	1750	6.13	1.39

The analysis of fertilizer utilization among farmers shows a clear preference for specific products. Single Super Phosphate (SSP) is the most utilized fertilizer, accounting for 25.45% of total usage due to its role in enhancing phosphorus levels, crucial for leguminous crops. Following SSP, Diammonium Phosphate (DAP) contributes significantly with 24.96% of usage, valued for its nitrogen and phosphorus content, particularly beneficial in early crop growth. Urea, a major nitrogen source, ranks third, comprising 22.46% of the total

share. The balanced nutrient profile of NPK 10-26-26 supports reproductive phases, while lesser-used fertilizers indicate specialized applications. Other fertilizers such as 20-20-0-13, 18-18-10, and MOP show lower utilization, with shares of 9.60%, 0.83%, and 1.39%, respectively, indicating their more specialized or limited use among farmers. This highlights the trend towards multi-nutrient fertilizers among farmers.

Table 11: Evaluation of Received Linked Products

Sr. No.	Linked products	Quantity (lit.)	Price per unit (Rs.)	Average per farmer (lit.)	Total value per farmer (Rs.)
1	Nano Urea	63	250	1.05	262.50
2	Liquid Consortia (Bio-Fertilizer)	66	350	1.10	385.00

The table (11) indicates that Nano Urea, with 63 liters utilized at Rs. 250 per liter, shows moderate usage among farmers, totaling Rs. 262.50. In contrast, Liquid Consortia has higher utilization with 66 liters at Rs. 350 each, amounting to Rs. 385.00. This suggests a greater

reliance on Liquid Consortia, possibly due to perceived benefits, despite its higher cost. The data reflects varying expenditure patterns on these products, with Liquid Consortia resulting in higher overall costs for farmers.

4.3 The farmers perception about linked products

Table 12: Assessment of farmers perception about linked products

Sr. No.	Particulars	Yes	No
1	Extra Cost	55 (91.67)	5 (8.33)
2	Product Awareness	54 (90)	6 (10)
3	Credit Period	40 (66.67)	20 (33.33)
4	Useful	45 (75)	15 (25)
5	Result	45 (75)	15 (25)
6	Forcefully Purchased	0 (0)	60 (100)
7	Timely Availability	45 (75)	15 (25)

Figures in parentheses are in percentage.

Farmers exhibit a strong awareness of agricultural products, with 90% being knowledgeable. However, a high percentage (91.67%) incur extra costs, which can impact their overall financial health. Access to credit is moderate, with 66.67% of farmers utilizing this option. While 75% find the products useful, 25% express dissatisfaction, indicating room for improvement. Importantly, purchases are voluntary, and 75% of farmers report timely product availability, although some face delays. Overall, while farmers are generally informed and empowered in their purchasing decisions, they still encounter challenges that affect their agricultural practices.

Conclusion

The demographic profile of farmers shows that a majority are middle-aged and possess a relatively high level of education. This educated cohort, combined with substantial awareness of agricultural technologies, creates a conducive environment for adopting modern practices. However, the predominance of medium-sized farms suggests a need for tailored support in agrochemical solutions to optimize productivity. The income distribution highlights financial constraints, necessitating cost-effective solutions. Despite a high level of awareness regarding fertilizers and agricultural products, the incurred extra costs and resource access challenges reflect ongoing barriers that farmers face in improving their agricultural practices.

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